

The Concept of Disability in Libyan Culture

Zeinab Abulhul

Georg Mason University, United States

ABSTRACT

The author delves into the perspectives of Libyan parents regarding children with disabilities. The article highlights the impact of Libyan culture on the kind of disability and how society views children with disabilities and their parents in the Libyan community. An analytical thinking framework was used to analyze the extent to which societal culture has impacted the social lives of Libyan citizens. Some people's attitudes toward having children with disabilities in their families or relatives are influenced by their family structure, while others are influenced by their social connections and norms. Furthermore, the article examines how members of the close Libyan family, such as mothers, fathers, and siblings, perceive disability and how their opinions affect individuals with disabilities. The aim of this article is to educate social workers about the impact of societal culture on the treatment of children with disabilities. This knowledge can help them advocate for these children with the government and utilize resources more effectively.

Keywords: social connections, norms, social workers, parents, culture, community, society, treatment, advocate, government, resources.

INTRODUCTION

Culture is a complicated concept that has various meanings. According to the definition given by Edward B. Tylor (1871), culture is “that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, law, morals, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society” (as cited in Spencer-Oatey, 2012: Tylor, 1874 digitalized 2007). Culture involves people’s lifestyles, thoughts, and impressions. Therefore, culture helps individuals visualize and understand social concepts based on their interactions with each other within their social environment. In this way, people conceptualize disability according to their thoughts and beliefs, which are influenced by the thoughts and beliefs of others with whom they share a culture.

Some parents who have a child with a disability believe that their child’s disability is a consequence of something wrong the parents have done in their lives. Meanwhile, other parents believe that having a child with a disability is not a cause for concern. They recognize that their children’s growth is slow, but they feel that the child will catch up with time (Diken, 2006). This cultural inventory presents itself in people’s experiences, social norms, and the religious values of society through informal social institutions (e.g., family, school, friends, and neighbors), which influence how people think, dress, eat, interact, and behave around others (Danseco, 2006). These influences, in turn, are reflected in people’s political decisions and economic plans. Most Libyan people are Muslim, and they are aware that Islam urges Muslims to take care of vulnerable people, including those with disabilities. However, their behaviors may still be

influenced by the Arab culture as much or more than by Islamic instructions, which has been attributed to ancient historical roots (Crabtree & Williams, 2011). According to ancient Libyan culture, having a child with a disability is attributed to acts of witchcraft – such as the casting of a spell on a family – God’s will, and supernatural occurrences (Etieyibo & Omiegbe, 2016). The nature of these beliefs has prevented people from having open and public conversations about having children with disabilities and the related needs and rights. When parents do find themselves in a situation in which they must speak about a child’s disability, they tend to stay silent to maintain a peaceful social atmosphere and to avoid being pointed out as having a disability in their family (Alghoul, 2016). This is especially true when the child is mentally ill or female (Al Khatib, 2016).

IMPACT OF THE LIBYAN FAMILY STRUCTURE ON THE TREATMENT OF INDIVIDUALS WITH DISABILITIES

Family Structure

There are four types of family units in the family structure of Libyan society. The “nuclear family” includes a father, mother, and their children. The “extended family” includes a father, mother, adult children, unmarried children, along with married children (and their children); an extended family lives together in one big house. The “big family” includes many nuclear and extended family members. They have the same last name and live in separate houses. The final family unit is the “tribe,” which includes several families with different last names but a shared line of descent (Hammad et al., 1999).

There are four factors that contribute to the formation of Libyan families’ attitudes toward individuals with disabilities. First, social values are essential in Libyan culture. For example, a strong family reputation allows a family to be proud of their members among other families, but any stigma connected to one person in a family can affect the whole family’s reputation. Second, the Libyan family structure encourages family members to create strong social ties through, for example, altruistic behaviors and collective efficacy. Thus, if any member of a family does something shameful, their family’s social ties could be negatively affected. Third, if a family, or one of its members, does not respect social norms and creates a stigma or a feeling of shame around the tribe, the entire tribe could be negatively affected for many years. Fourth, most Libyan families are Muslim and practice Islamic instructions. This factor has a positive impact on Libyans’ attitudes toward individuals with disabilities and may cause their attitudes to fluctuate (Benomir et al., 2016).

Parents of children with disabilities usually depend on their relatives to assist them, as social institutions consider disabilities a family issue. Family assistance emerged in Libya based on two ideas. The first is the Islamic idea that all Muslims should act as one body and help each other; the second is the cultural ideal that if a family member is stigmatized because of an impairment, it should affect the child’s extended family’s members. Thus, family members assist one another to protect the family’s reputation (Madi et al., 2019).

Treatment of children with disabilities by their families

Raising children with disabilities without support burdens Libyan families psychologically, physically, and financially. Parents who rear children with disabilities work hard to provide appropriate care to their children, which is often associated with feelings of shame. This feeling increases the stress involved in meeting children’s needs, particularly in terms of the roles and

contributions of mothers and non-disabled siblings during social occasions. In many Libyan families, fathers assign the responsibility of raising a disabled child to their wives, believing that it is the wife's fault that their child is disabled. Some husbands instead consider getting divorced, which increases the pressure put on a mother. In turn, the mother might reflect her negative feelings regarding her poor treatment toward her child (Reichman et al., 2008).

In many cases, mothers give up their work and withdraw from social contributions to allocate the time required to raise their children. They do this because they believe that their primary role is to help their children in the home while leaving working outside the home to their husbands. This way, the family can cover the expenses of raising the child while avoiding social interaction. These negative attitudes toward individuals with disabilities may lead to feelings of guilt. They may think that their disability prevents their parents from social engagements, and they feel that they are the cause of their family's social difficulties (Gharaibeh, 2009).

Libyan mothers may reject a newborn upon realizing that the child is disabled. Groce et al. (2014) suggested that some mothers may not breastfeed children who they do not think will contribute to their life. Families are afraid of failing to display social qualities that have been deemed acceptable by Libyan society and that improve a family's social acceptance and social status (e.g., health, wealth, generosity, and family reputation) (Lawson, 2011; Benomir et al., 2016). Parents' negative expectations of their children's social productivity and ability to be independent may shape their attitudes toward the personality of their child. This restricted impression may lead individuals with disabilities to think that they are useless to their families and that there is nothing they can do to change their parents' negative attitudes and meet their expectations (Coleridge, 2009).

Consequently, many Libyans pity families who rear children with disabilities and look upon them with somewhat shameful feelings. As a result, families may try to keep their children at home and teach them social skills before they are integrated into society. They believe that isolation preserves the family's reputation and prevents negative feelings (Crabtree & Williams, 2011). Furthermore, many parents believe that individuals with disabilities cannot be independent. Many parents also believe that they can provide the best conditions for their children at home and that they know what is best for their children. Thus, they make decisions on behalf of their children without consulting them in any way (Saad & Beszta, 2019). This situation leads some individuals with disabilities to voluntarily accept segregation, while others feel that they are forcibly prevented from having a social life.

Cultural Context, Social Ties, and Social Norms

Meeting Social Standards:

According to Patel (2000), an individual's identity is formed by several social elements, which play a significant role in one's interactions with their community. These social elements are associated with individuals' biological and social appearances. These appearances influence their personality and are reflected in their impressions about their community, their interactions with others within the social environment, and their behaviors in various social contexts. In addition, these social elements foster commonality and social ties among individuals living in one community based on shared experiences and knowledge about their community's history and social systems. As such, these elements shape people's individual identities (as cited in Masolo, 2002).

The roots of ancient Arab culture contain values that have influenced Libyans' identities, as described by Patel (2000). These cultural roots – which are reflected in one's bravery, generosity, pride, reproductive capacity, family status, and other characteristics – are still valid in Libyans' character today. Libyans consider these values a measurement tool for social status, family reputation, and social acceptance. Thus, Libyan people strive to obtain an ideal social image. The reasons for this go beyond factors related to social image itself. For example, a negative social image affects a family member's marriage prospects. Also, it affects what kind of children they expect to have and their social future (Mitchell, 2005). Therefore, most Libyan people work hard to achieve the ideal social image while denying anything that would harm their image. This desire for a positive social image can cause parents to ignore or hide a child's impairment.

Shame and Family Honor:

Feelings of shame, guilt, embarrassment, discomfort, and inferiority are especially unpleasant when they are part of a social punishment for failing to meet a perfect model determined by society (Golden, 2017). Therefore, many Libyan families make painstaking efforts to hide their social problems to avoid shame and embarrassment. According to Libyan culture, Libyan people perceive a family who raises disabled children as pathetic. They see a disabled child as a sign that the family has many historical, social, and health issues that have negatively affected their luck and their children's future. This extends to their marital prospects and family honor. As such, if a family includes a disabled child, this can negatively affect other member's potential marriages because it is believed that the disability is inherited from their original family and will be passed down to their future children. In some cases, fathers of a disabled child take a second wife to ensure that they do not have more children with disabilities (Al-Krenawi & Graham, 2000).

Denial:

Libyan families who know that they have a disabled child commonly deny the disability and tend to blame those who diagnose their child. For example, a schoolteacher who expresses concern about a child's understanding and behavior and then advises the parents to visit a pediatrician is often blamed for not providing suitable teaching strategies to evaluate the child's understanding (Logsdon, 2019).

Many Libyan parents are reluctant to acknowledge that they are rearing a child with disability. However, some parents are proactive if nearby families exhibit tolerance (Mitchell, 2005). Other families refuse to rear disabled children to avoid bad luck. According to Crabtree (2007), many people believe that having disabled children is a sign of divine punishment. This is especially true of husbands who blame their wives for and then distance themselves from their wives (as cited in Raddawi, 2015). This situation instills a feeling of guilt in the wives, who are made to believe that they did something wrong.

Fatalism:

Fatalism is the belief, common in Islam, that a person's conditions are beyond their control, meaning that a person is not to blame for problematic events (White, 2015). Thus, some Libyan families believe that raising children with disabilities is the family's fate and a sign of God's reward to increase their wealth and success. According to Dala and Pande (1999), Berry (2005), and Nirit and Shunit (2013), people believe in fatalism, meaning that a family who has a child

with a disability attributes the disability to God's will and perceives it as a way to be closer to God. Thus, many people who think that having a child with a disability is the family's fate and a result of God's will do not expect professional intervention to make any difference in their child's life (Mitchell & Brown, 2013).

FAMILY MEMBERS' PERSPECTIVES OF DISABILITY

Mothers' Perspectives

Libyan family members have strong social ties, which makes each family member aware of their social roles in relation to each other. Mothers take care of their family members' affairs, while fathers provide for family needs (Marini & Stebnicki, 2017). The influence of Islam makes Libyan parents think that having a child with a disability is a test from God and that they should be responsible for their children's well-being. This leads many Libyan mothers to accept the role of caretaker to their disabled children out of fear of punishment from God (Ahmed et al., 2013). This causes many disabled children to become marginalized as a result of their parents' negative expectations and lack of knowledge about disabled children's needs (Madi, Mandy, & Aranda, 2019; Matt, 2014).

Fathers' Perspectives

There is not much research about father's attitudes towards disabled children, as most research on disabled children treats the father and mother as one unit. Libyan fathers consider childcare the primary responsibility of mothers, with fathers playing a secondary role in children's well-being. The primary roles of fathers are to be good providers and decision-makers for the family and to serve as role models for their children (Navalkar, 2004: Learning disabilities, LD OnLine, 2019). Some fathers who have a newborn with a disability attribute the situation to God's will and accept it as their personal fate to avoid social stigma (Al-Aoufi, Al-Zyoud, & Shahminan, 2012). Fathers often feel stressed, disappointed, and neglected when their wives give considerable attention to their disabled children, leaving no room for intimacy between husband and wife. As a result, divorce is usually considered (Ritchie, 2013).

Fathers tend to be passive in such situations and remain silent, rarely expressing their feelings to their wives. These feelings cause fathers to avoid social obligations by working long hours under the pretext that they are helping their family financially (Pelchat, Lefebvre, & Perreault, 2003). Fathers reject their child's impairment and overlook the daily care by avoiding social situations in which they could compare themselves with parents of non-disabled children who are overtly proud. Fathers of disabled sons do not expect the disabled child to become healthy men who meet the social norm that dictates that a son should be healthy and strong like his father (Peters, 2013; Responsible Fatherhood Spotlight, 2010). According to Sharpet et al. (2006), some fathers of disabled children fall into a vicious cycle of self-blame and rejection, which can turn into negative attitudes toward the disabled child (as cited in Beatty & King, 2008).

Siblings' Perspectives

Siblings' attitudes toward their siblings with disabilities differ based on age. Siblings are expected to play, speak, and do activities together, as well as to express their feelings, joys, curiosities, and fears. When a non-disabled sibling does not have these kinds of interactions with a sibling, they start to worry. They then start to compare their disabled sibling with other siblings and relatives, as well as with their neighbors and peers at school. These comparisons

lead non-disabled siblings to infer that there is something wrong with their disabled siblings. The non-disabled sibling is often curious to find out what is wrong by asking their parents questions about their sibling's disability.

When non-disabled siblings are relatively young, they might feel jealous that their parents pay more attention and provide more care to their disabled siblings. This can occur even if the parents explain the situation to the non-disabled child. The subsequent feelings of unfairness, worthlessness, and rejection cause non-disabled children to isolate themselves and assume the role of observer of the family's interactions (Brinkmann, 2019).

As non-disabled siblings grow older, they come to understand the situation from experiencing their parents' and close relatives' attitudes toward their disabled siblings. Thus, they try not to behave like their disabled siblings as to not upset their parents. They might hide their feelings in an attempt to act based on their parents' attitudes toward their disabled siblings. They might even start to share their parents' feelings of shame when their disabled sibling does not act according to social expectations. Thus, they will often try to formulate excuses for the misbehavior of their disabled siblings (Meltzer & Kramer, 2016; Milevsky, 2014).

The cultural perspective shows how Libyan attitudes toward children with disabilities have been influenced implicitly by ancient history and Islamic religion as present Libyan culture

CONCLUSION

This article discusses the definition of culture as presented by Edward B. Tylor in 1871. It emphasizes how social interactions within a specific environment shape people's understanding of social concepts. In Libyan society, cultural components affect how individuals perceive their societal culture, particularly in regard to attitudes toward children with disabilities. The article delves into how cultural influence shapes the views of special needs children's parents towards their disabled children and their expectations surrounding the disability. Attitudes towards children with disabilities are influenced by family structure, relationships, social connections, and norms. The article aims to provide social workers with insights into the importance of cultural considerations when working with special needs children. It also aims to equip them with practical strategies to advocate for their educational rights and support their parents in providing greater independence for their children with special needs while helping them feel included in their society. Additionally, the article calls for social work researchers to investigate the impact of community culture on attitudes toward special needs education and to enhance community libraries with literature on people's perceptions towards children with disabilities.

References

- [1]. Ahmed, S., Bryant, L., Ahmed, M., Jafri, H., & Raashid, H. (2013). Experiences of parents with a child with Down Syndrome in Pakistan and their views on termination of pregnancy. *PMC*. 4(1). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3537972/>
- [2]. Al Khatib, J. M. (2016). Arab American children with disabilities: Considerations for teachers and service providers. *Routledge*. https://books.google.com/books?id=L2-3DAAAQBAJ&dq=how+arab+culture+treat+disabled+children&source=gbs_navlinks_s

- [3]. Al-Aoufi, H., Al-Zyoud, N., & Shahminan, N. (2012). Islam and the cultural conceptualization of disability. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2011.649565>
- [4]. Alghoul, D. (2016). Fighting the taboo of disability in the Arab world. *Europe & Russia, International Organizations, Interviews*, UK. <https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20161203-fighting-the-taboo-of-disability-in-the-arab-world/>
- [5]. Al-Krenawi, A. & Graham, J. R. (2000). Culturally sensitive social work practice with Arab clients in mental health settings. *National Association of Social Workers*. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.476.3269&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [6]. Beatty, D., & King, A. (2008). Supporting fathers who have a child with a disability: The development of a new parenting program. *Groupwork*, 18(3). <https://www.groupworksolutions.com.au/s/Supporting-fathers-who-have-a-child-with-a-disability-The-development-of-a-new-parenting-program.pdf>
- [7]. Benomir, A. M., Nicolson, R. I., & Beail, N. (2016) Attitudes towards people with intellectual disability in the UK and Libya: A cross-cultural comparison. *White Rose University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK*. http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/95227/3/WRRO_95227.pdf
- [8]. Berry, J. W. (2005). Disability attitudes, beliefs and behaviors: Preliminary report on an international project in community-based rehabilitation. (Doctoral dissertation, Queen's University). https://unipd-centrodirittiumani.it/public/docs/23636_cbr.pdf
- [9]. Brinkmann, J. (2019). How does having a sibling with a disability impact quality of life? *The O&P Edge*. <https://progress.oandp.com/Articles/ViewArticle/2019-08-01/how-does-having-a-sibling-with-a-disability-impact-quality-of-life>
- [10]. Coleridge, P. T. (2009). Disability and culture. *Semantic Scholar*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/DISABILITY-AND-CULTURE-Coleridge/1236e5ba0b31063cc21e5b868b2cf02d6077a962>
- [11]. Crabtree, S. A. (2007). Maternal perceptions of caregiving of children with developmental disabilities in the United Arab Emirates. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 20, 247–255. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3148.2006.00327.x>
- [12]. Crabtree, S., & Williams, R. (2011). Ethical implications for research into inclusive education in Arab societies: Reflections on the politicization of the personalized research experience. *International Social Work*, 56(2), 148-161. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872811416486>
- [13]. Dalal, A. K., & Pande, N. (1999). Cultural beliefs and family care of the children with Disability. *Psychology and Developing Societies*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/097133369901100103>
- [14]. Danseco, E. (2006). Parental beliefs on childhood disability: Insights on culture, child development and intervention. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 44(1), 41-52, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0156655970440104>
- [15]. Diken, I. H. (2006). Review of research: An overview of parental perceptions in cross-cultural groups on disability. *Childhood Education*, 82(4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00094056.2006.10522831>
- [16]. Etieyibo, E., & Omiegbe, O. (2016). Religion, culture, and discrimination against person with disabilities in Nigeria. *African Journal of Disability*, 5(1), 192. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5433448/>
- [17]. Gharaibeh, N. (2009). Disability in Arab societies. *Research Gate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/290165220>

- [18]. Golden, B. (2017). Overcoming the paralysis of toxic shame. *Psychology Today*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/overcoming-destructive-anger/201704/overcoming-the-paralysis-toxic-shame>
- [19]. Groce, N., London, J., & Stein, M. (2014). Inheritance, poverty, and disability. *Disability & Society*, 29(10), 1554-1568. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2014.969831>
- [20]. Hammad, A., Kysia, R., Rabah, R., Hassoun, R., & Connelly, M. (1999). Guide to Arab culture: Health care delivery to the Arab American community. *ACCESS Community Health Center*. https://www.accesscommunity.org/sites/default/files/documents/health_and_research_cente_21.pdf
- [21]. Lawson, J. (2011). Disability as a cultural identity. *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, 11(3), 203-222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09620210100200076>
- [22]. Learning disabilities, LD On Line. (2019). *How to maximize fathers' involvement with their children who have disabilities*. <http://www.ldonline.org/article/5935/>
- [23]. Logsdon, A. (2019). Common parent reactions to a child's learning disability. *Very Well Family*. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/parent-reactions-childs-disability-2162643>
- [24]. Madi, S., Mandy, A., & Aranda, K. (2019). The perception of disability among mothers living with a child with cerebral palsy in Saudi Arabia. *Global Qualitative Nursing Research*, 6. [https://doi: 10.1177/2333393619844096](https://doi.org/10.1177/2333393619844096)
- [25]. Marini, I., & Stebnicki, M. (2017). *The psychological and social impact of illness and disability* (7th ed). Springer Publishing Company. <https://books.google.com/books?id=WlYxDwAAQBAJ&pg=PA158&lpg=PA158&dq=what+is+the+difference+attitudes+of+Arab+people+toward+disabled+boys+or+girls&source=bl&ots=1sxDjA58H&sig=ACfU3U3Y20s3ewmh0ke7->
- [26]. Masolo, D. A. (2002). Community, identity, and the cultural space. *Cairn Info*. [https://doi: 10.3917/rdes.036.0019](https://doi.org/10.3917/rdes.036.0019)
- [27]. Matt, S., (2014). Perceptions of disability among caregivers of children with disabilities in Nicaragua: Implications for future opportunities and health care access. *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 34(4). <http://dsq-sds.org/article/view/3863/3799>
- [28]. Meltzer, A., & Kramer, J. (2016). Siblinghood through disability studies perspectives: diversifying discourse and knowledge about siblings with and without disabilities. *Disability & Society*, 31(1), 17–32. <http://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2015.1127212>
- [29]. Milevsky, A. (2014). Siblings of children with disabilities. *Psychology Today*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/band-brothers-and-sisters/201406/siblings-children-disabilities>
- [30]. Mitchell, D., & Brown, R. (2013). *Early intervention studies for young children with special needs*. Springer. <https://books.google.com/books?id=1RX3BwAAQBAJ&pg=PA69&lpg=PA69&dq=fatal>
- [31]. Mitchell, D. (2005). *Contextualizing inclusive education evaluating old and new international paradigms*. Routledge. London. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203606803>
- [32]. Navalkar, P. (2004). Fathers' perception of their role in parenting a child with cerebral palsy: Implications for counselling. *International Journal for the Advancement of Counselling*. 26(4), 375- 378. [https://doi: 10.1007/s10447-004-0173-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10447-004-0173-y)

- [33]. Nirit, K., & Shunit, R. (2013). Attitudes towards Autism among Israeli Arab teachers' college students. In M. Fitzgerald (Ed.). *Recent Advances in Autism Spectrum Disorders*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/54845>
- [34]. Pelchat, D., Lefebvre, H., & Perreault, M. (2003). Differences and similarities between mothers' and fathers' experiences of parenting a child with a disability. *Journal of Child Health Care*, 7(4), 231-247. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/13674935030074001>
- [35]. Peters, S. (2013). *Education and disability in cross-cultural perspective*. Routledge. https://books.google.com/books?id=PYwuAgAAQBAJ&pg=PA193&dq=Fathers%E2%80%99+cultural+perspective+of++disabled+children&hl=en&newbks=1&newbks_redir=0&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjQ1KeGk-
- [36]. Raddawi, R. (2015). *Intercultural communication with Arabs: Studies in educational, professional and societal contexts*. New York: Springer. https://books.google.com/books?id=umPEBQAAQBAJ&pg=PA331&lpg=PA331&dq=disabled+children+considered+shame+for+Arab+families&source=bl&ots=BublxXXPr_&sig=ACfU3U34A0ZF04
- [37]. Reichman, N. E., Corman, H., & Noonan, K. (2008). Impact of child disability on the family. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 12(6), 679-683. https://www.medscape.com/viewarticle/581577_2
- [38]. Responsible Fatherhood Spotlight. (2010). Father involvement – children with disabilities <http://dhhs.nv.gov/uploadedFiles/dhhsnv.gov/content/Programs/IDEA/ProjectASSIST/2010Feb-Father%20Involvement-ChildrenwithDisabilitiesUSDeptofHHSA.pdf>
- [39]. Ritchie, M. (2013). Children born with disabilities: How families respond. *Child Research Net*. https://www.childresearch.net/papers/rights/2013_01.html
- [40]. Saad, M., & Beszta, B. (2019). Disability in the Arab world: A comparative analysis within culture. *International Journal of Psycho-Educational Sciences*, 8(2). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334824030_Disability_in_the_Arab_World_A_Comparative_Analysis_within_Culture
- [41]. Tylor, S. (1874 digitalized 2007). *Primitive culture: Research into the development of Mythology, Philosophy, Religion, Language, Art and Custom*. (Vol. 1). Harvard University. https://books.google.com/books?id=ungPAAAAYAAJ&printsec=frontcover&dq=inauthor:%22Edward+Burnett+Tylor%22&hl=en&newbks=1&newbks_redir=0&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjX7efOu-LIAhVooFkKHfG8CKMQuwUwAHoECAMQBQ#v=onepage&q&f=false
- [42]. White, L. (2015). Are Muslim Arabs Especially Fatalistic? [web blog]. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/culture-conscious/201503/are-muslim-arabs-especially-fatalistic>